

FAIR/CARE Principles as Normative Ethics in Digital Musicology

MEI, Metadata, and Minimising Invisible Labour

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Given the highly collaborative nature of (digital) scholarship, crediting those who contribute to the creation or lifecycle of any project is an ethical imperative. As such, labor visibility is and remains a critical topic, especially as digital scholarship continues to evolve and define itself. To ask questions of musical creative or intellectual outputs, analogue or digital, necessitates an understanding of both their nature and the circumstances of their creation. Filmmaker Hollis Frampton's assessment of photographic snapshots applies to multi-faceted scholarly undertakings. Each one "purports to be an ideal...wholly static cross section through a four-dimensional solid, or tesseract, of unimaginable intricacy." (Frampton, 2009, 27) Critical editions, collected works, and other similar projects are such printed tesseracts in musicology. Often in these projects, praise for a managing editors approaches apotheosis as singularly visionary titans. Martin Staehelin's review of Edwin Lowinsky's three-volume edition of *The Medici Codex* for the *Journal of the American Musicological Society* lauds the editor profoundly.

At every step it reveals the characteristic expertise and the superior synthetic powers of a scholar intimately familiar with his subject, committed to it in a deeply personal way, and sparing no effort in his musicological work. Without a doubt Edwin Lowinsky has in this critical edition of the *Medici Codex* lived up to his motto of achieving only the best and...has...actually achieved the best that present-day research in the music of the Renaissance can hope to attain. (Staehelin, 1980, 587)

In addition to its historiography of the AMS, Staehelin's review highlights that he was acting as an arbiter of quality within a community of scholars, thereby evincing Pierre Bourdieu's stipulation of taste as a cultural construct mo-

derated by gatekeepers who are also often competitor-colleagues. (Bourdieu, 1984) Anyone who engages with artistic/intellectual works operates within **art worlds**, which generate art as entity, process, and experience. (Becker, 1982) These communities enact a myriad of collaborative and individual processes, the absence of any of which alters the final output. Considering their nature and operations as the miniature societies they are is invaluable.

Normative Ethics

Social contractalism thus applies, as it offers tools for assessing and constructing societal normative ethics. T.M. Scanlon's reasonable rejectability is a useful barometer for demarcating right from wrong. "An act is wrong if its performance under the circumstances would be disallowed by any set of principles for the general regulation of behaviour that no one could reasonably reject as a basis for informed, unforced, general agreement." (Scanlon, 1998, 153) In Scanlon's work, moreover, "One reason for focusing on wrong is to draw attention to the domain that contractalism is concerned to map, concerning what it is for one person to have been wronged by another." (Ashford and Mulgan, 2018)

For creative or intellectual projects, invisible labour is just such a wrong, even as it has proliferated across disciplines, especially in the space of single author or editor publications. Even in multi-author work, the full accounting of roles of non-authorial contributors is often absent for various reasons, resulting in invisible labour. As such, any accurate and thus honest intellectual history of research outputs is often not possible. One way to a solution adopts John Rawls's **original position** behind the **veil of ignorance**. By not knowing one's potential role in (academic) society, one is more likely to pursue the goal of en-framing justice as Heideggerian *Gestell* through developing fair governing principles to which everyone agrees. "...Fair terms of cooperation specify an idea of reciprocity or mutuality...The idea of rational advantage specifies that it is that those engaged in cooperation are seeking to advance from the standpoint of their own good." (Rawls, 2001, 6) Rawls leverages self-interest from the position of ignorance to epitomise justice in the form of fairness to all. (Ashford and Mulgan, 2018)

Both Scanlon and Rawls seek to enframe societies along the lines of fairness and justice where the two concepts co-define each other. The FAIR and CARE principles for data offer a tandem approach for normative ethics of research community governance. FAIR's emphases on metadata under Findable and Accessible are notable. ("FAIR Principles, 2021) Metadata must be rich and accessible even when data they describe might no longer exist. The CARE principles focus more on the rights of people involved in research, both subjects and practitioners. ("CARE Principles," 2019) In many ways, the focus here is on constructive collaboration, namely honest attribution and equitably shared governance. The FAIR principles thus seek to create a technological enframement in which the CARE principles are

readily attainable, eventually becoming the norm in research praxis.

Metadata and MEI

Metadata is the appropriate locus for crediting contributions associated with intellectual labour, especially taking the FAIR and CARE principles as normative ethics. The Music Encoding Initiative offers numerous affordances in this regard. Because MEI has become the standard format for high quality musical data and metadata only in the past ten-to-fifteen years, is community-driven, and dedicated to principles of fairness evinced by (and derived from) Rawls and Scanlon, it is also ideally situated for future projects.

One significant tool emergent from the MEI community is the Metadata editor and repository for MEI data – MerMEId, which was developed primarily for use in the Catalogue of Carl Nielsen’s Works. (Catalogue of Carl Nielsen’s Works, 2018) Here, one can create and enrich metadata for a work’s history in terms of people, places, etc., along with an intellectual history of engagements with it. Making these designations possible are the options in the contributor panels in the work and file tabs of the editor. A person’s role is fully customisable via the attribute editor, as are other descriptors. Furthermore, linking to authority data sources is readily available for works histories. Adapting Hollis Frampton’s analysis of images as both objects in their own right and as semiotic icons or indices to this aesthetic space reveals how this flexibility matters. A musical work or source is “like language, doubly identified: once with itself, and once again with its referent.” (Frampton, 2009, 71) Ongoing and planned further developments for the MerMEId aim to make it more adaptable and easier to enrich for project-specific needs.

In addition to role attributes or ORCID IDs as authority data, one can also easily leverage the MEI schema to offer plain text descriptions of contributions to a project in either the file description (Figure 1) or the revision description (Figure 2).

The flexibility and economy of digital metadata, especially in MEI, to make labour more visible reflects one of Frampton’s strongest appreciations of work in photography, where he focused on collections and inventories in a manner similar to constructing both narrowly focused projects or broadly-focused collected or complete editions. “The artist reaffirms his own existence through gradually replacing the space of the given world with the inventory of spaces of all the photographs he has made.” (Frampton, 2009, 75) Changing ‘artist’ for ‘researcher’ and ‘photograph’ for ‘project’ or ‘Ausgabe’ does not undermine Frampton’s point.

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33 </mei>

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Figure 1. <fileDesc> contributor accounting in <meiHead> for contributions at/ embedded in file creation (beginning of file).

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Figure 2. <change>, <persName>, and <changeDesc> in <revisionDesc> for changes made after file creation (end of file).

Musicological praxis is moving in this direction, albeit slowly, especially in the space of corpus-study based projects such as critical editions and works catalogues. Major canonical composers have heretofore been the overwhelming focal point for such projects, many of which still feature single-editor acknowledgement. Additional contribution acknowledgements almost always reside in a preface or a footnote, namely the data contents, rather than metadata. Mentions in the object data, whether primary or supplementary material, are the norm, and are useful means of crediting contributions from various persons attached to a project. However, locating such mentions solely in the data content creates a credit differential with scholars mentioned in the metadata.

The exclusion of these contributors from the metadata creates an incomplete intellectual history that falls short of FAIR adherence for: 1) Findability’s “Rich metadata,” 2) Accessibility’s “Metadata outliving data,” 3) Interoperability’s “Qualified references to other data and metadata,” and 4) Reusability’s “rich and accurate descriptions of data,” “detailed provenance,” and “domain-relevant community standards.” Through understanding benefits and pitfalls of different eras of project inception and variable external guidelines (expectations of funding agencies), and learning from them, envisaging and working toward a more equitable operational model is possible.

Ways Forward

Obstacles persist and are intertwined with ongoing misunderstandings about the nature of digital tools and infrastructures—namely that, for many, digital work exists as a kind of machina-ex-deus. As such, and because it is not always as integral to musicological projects, it can often seem unworthy of the credit it is due. (Luhmann and Burghardt, 2021, 149) Community labour, especially digital, either fa-

des or is pushed to the background too easily, creating an opportunity, if not obligation, for education about the nature of digital work and the rigour and creativity required to engage it.

Even as the digitality of some projects enhances the presence of FAIR and CARE principles in labour acknowledgement, the reality is that until the thinking of disciplinary gatekeepers evolves, the political, social, and disciplinary capital of print editions reigns supreme. As such, teaching and research activities are often negatively affected, especially in the case of tenure and promotion processes where review committees in music need guidance on evaluating digital work, and the guidance that exists needs more frequent updating than that for analogue work. These guidelines also, in turn, affect training opportunities for students, and the nature of capstone projects.

Digital scholars (including musicologists) do well, then, to adopt Hans Van Maanen's consideration of art worlds with foci on equal access and opportunity while emphasising the need to decentralise cultural power, i.e. – gatekeeping. (Maanen, 2010, 238) What is true as this discussion focuses on art making processes that perhaps centre aesthetic performance, remains true if one shifts the focus to research activity, whether analogue or digital. Rawls's difference principle, which dictates that the most fair and just distribution is the one where the least-advantaged group does best, is a useful metric. Adapting van Maanen's considerations of interactions between art worlds and their social-political contexts to the scope of (digital) musicology, especially with the need to educate academic gatekeepers might results in a three-fold approach:

1. Recognizing music scholarship as aesthetic and scholarly communication. This recognition in turn requires guaranteeing access to contributor status, within appropriate guidelines for academic rigour and technological engagement.

2. Shifting paradigms toward greater FAIR/CARE inclusion as fundamental principles via ethical and technological education. Beyond the inherent need for technological education in the making phase consumption skills (how to interact with and value) digital editions that are FAIR/CARE adherent is also necessary.

3. Continuing to decentralise the loci of cultural, educational, and publishing power away from the rapidly-becoming-antiquated model of for-profit print publishing by committing to open science, open source, and open access editions, at least as much as is feasible.

This paper thus advocates for increasing access to engaging scholarly praxis, and for receiving fair recognition in the metadata, while enhancing standards of scholarly rigour. Rather than suggesting a unilateral equivalency of attribution among contributors, since not all contributions are the same, it proposes that anyone who contributes intellectual labour deserves credit for their work. MEI's affordances for documenting metadata in musicological work make this credit easily giveable and customizable with only a few lines of code.

To be fully FAIR, any edition's data must be as rich and accurate as possible. Additionally, its metadata must be so, especially as it concerns recognizing the art world of its creation. Only then can a community begin to engage in the formal training necessary to contribute high quality data that is both interoperable and reusable at a technical level. These collaborative communities exist already, though to varying degrees of visibility. FAIR-ifying their metadata makes them more visible and, in so doing, also makes the normative ethics of FAIR and CARE more standard praxis than thought experiment. This kind of scholarly model, based on Becker's Art Worlds and infused with Rawls's and Scanlon's senses of social contractualism, exhorts ongoing assessment and adjustment of praxes—in musicological work, training, and pedagogy. Historiographical efforts thus also merit reconsideration. In the context of music scholarship, authors, editors, and all contributors are inextricable from their context. Leveraging MEI's metadata affordances for detailed and accurate intellectual histories of these communities and the works they engage enables more visibility for labour within them, an undergirding tenet of the FAIR and CARE principles. In sum, then, this paper offers perhaps no sweeping paradigm shift, but instead a few small steps toward a more just, community-based, and digital model of scholarly work in musicology.

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